

Spectrophotometric Determination of Manganese(II) with 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde Guanylhydrazone

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Manganese is estimated by spectrophotometric methods¹. It is determined using formaldoxime² and complexometrically with thiomalic acid indicator³. It is also determined by the extractive photometric methods with xanthates and salicylaldoxime.

Guanylhydrazones form complexes with transition metals⁴. The present communication deals with the application of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde guanylhydrazone (CSAG) for spectrophotometric determi-

nation of Mn^{II}. The reagent forms an intense yellow coloured complex at pH 9.5. The method is simple, rapid and highly sensitive for determination of Mn^{II} at trace level.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Mn^{II}-CSAG complex showed absorption maximum at 395 nm. At this wavelength the reagent solution has zero absorbance. The molar extinction coefficient was found to be $5.626 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The absorbance was maximum and remained constant in the pH range 7.8–12.4. Hence the pH 9.5 was selected for study. The complex was stable for several hours and about four-fold excess of the reagent was sufficient for full colour development of 2.0 ppm of Mn^{II}.

Beer's law is valid up to 9 ppm of Mn^{II}. The opti-

imum concentration range for determination of Mn was studied from the Ringbom plot⁵ and found to be 4.5–7.9 ppm. The Sandell sensitivity⁶ was found to be $0.08494 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The composition of the complex was determined by Job's continuous variation method⁷ and mole-ratio method⁸. The results indicate the formation of a single complex having the 1 : 2 (Mn^{II} : CSAG) composition.

The degree of dissociation⁹ was found to be 0.1081. The apparent instability constant¹⁰ was established from mole-ratio method, was found to be 6.767×10^{-11} . The change in free energy¹¹ of the system is $-13.868 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

Effect of diverse ions : In order to test the interferences Mn^{II} was determined in presence of foreign ions. An error up to $\pm 2.0\%$ in absorbance was considered to be tolerable. The interference of Ag^I was eliminated by 0.1% thiourea. Pd^{II} and Cu^{II} were masked with 5% sodium thiosulphate (2.0 ml), and Co^{II} with thiocyanate solution. It was found that chromium, iron and EDTA interfere seriously.

The Mn content of the mild steel sample (Mn, 0.5%) estimated by the present method was found to be 0.485%.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm matched pair of glass cuvetts was used. pH was measured on an Elico LI-120 pH meter.

Synthesis of CSAG : A mixture of aminoguanidine

bicarbonate (2.0 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (till evolution of CO₂ ceased) and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (2.3 g) dissolved in ethanol (10.0 ml), was kept for 1 h. The resulting yellow coloured solid was crystallised from ethanol, (~88%), m. p. 224–27°. The compound was found to be soluble in water and ethanol but insoluble in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. It showed satisfactory C, H, N and Cl analyses. The ionisation constant of the reagent (CSAG) was obtained both by spectrophotometric and by pH-metric methods. The p*K* value was obtained to be 11.4.

A stock solution of CSAG (0.01 *M*) was prepared in ethanol. A stock solution of Mn^{II} (1 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving manganese sulphate monohydrate in distilled water containing a few drops of H₂SO₄ and standardised volumetrically¹². Buffer solution was prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of boric acid and NaOH.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing 20 µg of Mn^{II}, was added 1.0 × 10⁻³ *M* CSAG (1.2 ml). The pH of the solution was then adjusted to 9.5 with buffer solution and diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the Mn^{II}-CSAG complex was measured at 395 nm against reagent blank, and Mn was determined from a calibration curve.

Mild steel sample (Ob.BAS England) (1.0 g) was dissolved in aquaregia (10.0 ml) on heating and the solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. A suitable aliquot (1.0 ml) was taken and Mn was determined by the recommended procedure. Iron was eliminated by precipitation method¹².

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References

1. J. J. MORGAN and W. STUMM, *J. Am. Wat. Wks. Assoc.*, 1965, **57**, 107.
2. E. MICHENKOVA, J. BOUDA and M. MIGOVA, *Cesk. Hvg.*, 1980, **25**, 42.
3. V. N. CHOUDHARY, N. N. GANGULY and L. P. PANDY, *J. Inst. Chem., Calcutta*, 1986, **58**, 15.
4. J. THIELE and E. DRALF, *Annalen*, 1898, **302**, 278.
5. L. MEITIS, "Hand Book of Analytical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963, pp. 6–17.
6. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 84.
7. P. JOB, *Compt. Rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
8. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
9. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
10. K. C. TRIKHA, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1967, **14**, 977.
11. A. A. GRINBERG, "An Introduction to the Chemistry of Complex Compounds", 2nd. ed., 1951, Translated by J. R. LEACH, Pergamon, London, 1962, p. 275.
12. "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., E.L.B.S., Longman, 1978.